

Level of Participation and Experiences on Inclusion of Minority Group Learners

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Abstract. This study examined the level of participation of minority group learners and their experiences of inclusion in selected public elementary schools in San Fernando, Bukidnon. Specifically, it aimed to determine the learners' profile, assess their participation in classroom activities, co-curricular programs, school events, and leadership roles, and explore their academic, social, and cultural inclusion. It also investigated whether differences in participation and inclusion exist based on grade level, gender, and minority status, and explored the relationship between participation and experiences of inclusion. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed. The respondents were 151 minority learners from Grades 4 to 6, purposively selected from six public elementary schools. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire adapted from previous studies, scored on a 4-point Likert scale, and analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean), inferential statistics (t-test, one-way ANOVA), and Pearson correlation. Findings revealed that minority learners actively participated in classroom activities and moderately participated in co-curricular activities, school events, and leadership roles. Their experiences of academic, social, and cultural inclusion were generally high. No significant differences in participation or inclusion were observed based on grade level or gender, while differences in leadership participation were noted according to minority status. Significant positive relationships were found between classroom participation and all dimensions of inclusion, while co-curricular and leadership roles were significantly related to social and cultural inclusion. Participation in school events was significantly associated with overall inclusion. The results suggest that active engagement, especially in classroom interactions, contributes to meaningful inclusion for minority learners. The study underscores the importance of inclusive teaching strategies, culturally responsive programs, and equitable leadership opportunities to promote holistic development, social integration, and empowerment among minority learners.

Introduction

Minority communities, such as Indigenous Peoples and other disadvantaged groups, are some of the most culturally diverse, yet underprivileged entities of the world. These groups usually share distinctive traditions, languages and knowledge systems which lead to cultural diversity and sustainability of the environment. However, they remain feel excluded and left out in the decision-making processes that directly impact their localities (United Nations, 2022). In order to achieve equity and sustainable development, it is important that they are involved in the governance and community planning.

On the global level, the key international documents, including the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People (UNDRIP) and the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development point out the necessity of inclusive participation and cultural diversity respect. In particular, Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 10 requires the decrease in inequalities inside and between nations, whereas SDG 16 encourages more inclusive and participative decision-making at every level (United

Nations, 2021). With these promises, the United Nations reports that minority and Indigenous groups continue to be underrepresented in the political, social, and economic life, especially in the third world countries (UNDP, 2020).

The Philippines understands the importance of minority groups in the nation-building processes at the national level by the adoption of the Indigenous Peoples Rights Act (IPRA) of 1997. This legislation ensures the ancestral rights, self-governance and cultural integrity of Indigenous Cultural Communities/Indigenous Peoples (ICCs/IPs). Nevertheless, research indicates that not all Indigenous and minority communities can participate authentically in the community planning and decision-making process (Carino, 2020, and Magno, 2022). Such obstacles are lack of representation, poor consultation processes and ignorance of the rights to participation. Although Philippine Development Plan (PDP) 2023-2028 promotes inclusive governance, there is a gap between the formulated policies to the real practice at the community level.

Inclusive development remains a challenge and an opportunity in Mindanao where the concentration of the Indigenous and minority populations is high. Although Indigenous communities have wealth in both natural resources and culture, they tend to be socio-economically marginalized and have little access to education, medical care, as well as political involvement (Brillantes & Cuachon, 2021). The lack of prior discussion and engagement with the minority sectors prior to implementing many community projects undermines the sustainability and cultural appropriateness of the development programs by Ponce (2022). It takes actual inclusion to mean that minority voices can be heard, incorporated in the community planning processes in a meaningful way.

The Higaonon tribes, Manobo tribes, and the Bukidnon tribes are minority groups in the Province of Bukidnon which are essential in the conservation of the environment and local governance. Nevertheless, even with the participation of the government, research has indicated that they usually engage in consultation and not decision-making by Sanchez, (2021) and Datu (2023). This is particularly common in such municipalities as San Fernando, where Indigenous population is large and at times the development projects border ancestral lands and practices. The generation of minority residents continues to be struggling in making their voices heard in the organization of activities because of lack of awareness, education, and logistics. Their participation should be enhanced so as to facilitate inclusive development that appreciates cultural diversity and the benefits of the progress should be shared by all members of the community.

In these settings, the current research paper entitled *The Level of Participation of Minority Groups and their experiences on Inclusion* aims to determine the level of participation of minority students in the school activities within the District 1 in San Fernando, Bukidnon and to learn about the life experience of these students in the learning institution, in terms of their inclusion and acceptance in the school. The research will also offer some insights to assist teachers, school leaders, and local education authorities in promoting more inclusive, equitable, and culturally responsive practices to support the engagement of minority learners and their general school life

Methodology

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. The descriptive method was used to determine the level of participation of minority group learners in classroom activities, co-curricular programs, school events, and leadership roles, as well as to describe their experiences of inclusion in terms of academic, social, and cultural aspects. The correlational method was applied to examine the relationship between the learners' level of participation and their experiences of inclusion.

The respondents of the study were 151 minority learners from Grades 4 to 6, enrolled in selected public elementary schools in the 1st District of San Fernando, Bukidnon during the School Year 2025–2026. A total enumeration sampling technique was employed, wherein all qualified minority learners who met the inclusion criteria were included in the study.

A structured questionnaire was used as the primary data-gathering instrument. The instrument was adapted and modified from the works of Kashem and Gallo (2023), Alcantara and Nelles (2014), and Cornell and Kalt (1998). It consisted of items measuring the learners' profile, level of participation, and experiences of inclusion. Responses were measured using a 4-point Likert scale to determine the extent of participation and inclusion.

Prior to data collection, permission was secured from the Schools Division Superintendent, district supervisors, and school administrators. Parental consent and learner assent were also obtained to ensure ethical compliance. The respondents were given sufficient time to answer the questionnaire, and confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the study.

The data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical tools. Frequency, percentage, and mean were used to describe the learners' profile, level of participation, and inclusion experiences. To determine significant differences, t-

test and one-way ANOVA were utilized. Pearson correlation was employed to examine the relationship between participation and inclusion.

Results and Discussion

The study involved 151 minority learners from Grades 4–6 in Bukidnon, San Fernando. The participants included 58 males (38.4%) and 93 females (61.6%), with the majority (72.8%) identified as Indigenous Peoples or other disadvantaged groups. Grade 6 had the highest representation (40.4%), followed by Grade 5 (30.5%) and Grade 4 (29.1%), providing a balanced distribution across grades and genders. Female predominance may have influenced engagement levels, consistent with literature suggesting that females tend to participate more actively in school activities (Luyt, 2011).

Grade	Frequency	Percent
4.00	44	29.1
5.00	46	30.5
6.00	61	40.4
Total	151	100.0
Sex		
Male	58	38.4
Female	93	61.6
Total	151	100.0
Minority		
1.00	110	72.8
2.00	34	22.5
3.00	7	4.6
Total	151	100.0

Table 2. The Profile of the Minority Group Learners in terms of Gender and Tribal Affiliation

Statement	Mean	SD	QD
I actively answer questions in class.	3.22	0.71	Most of the time
I participate in group discussions and activities.	3.42	0.65	Always
I complete my class tasks on time.	3.31	0.69	Always
Overall Mean	3.32	0.46	Always

Table 3. Level of Participation of Minority Group Learners in terms of Classroom Participation

Minority learners reported high engagement in classroom activities (Mean = 3.32, SD = 0.46). Group discussions and collaborative tasks were the most engaging (Mean = 3.42, SD = 0.65), whereas answering individual questions showed slightly lower engagement (Mean = 3.22, SD = 0.71). These findings align with Vygotsky’s Social Constructivist Theory, emphasizing social interaction as central to learning. Inclusive classroom practices enhance participation and peer cooperation (Gay, 2010; Ladson-Billings, 1995).

Statement	Mean	SD	QD
I join clubs, organizations, or school teams.	3.09	0.87	Most of the time
I participate in school contests or competitions.	3.16	0.80	Most of the time
Overall Mean	3.13	0.70	Most of the time

Table 4. Level of Participation of minority group learners in terms of Co-curricular activities

Participation in co-curricular activities was moderate (Mean = 3.13, SD = 0.70). Learners were slightly more involved in school contests (Mean = 3.16, SD = 0.80) than in clubs or organizations (Mean = 3.09, SD = 0.87). Limited engagement may reflect cultural, social, or self-efficacy barriers. Co-curricular involvement fosters social skills and belonging, supporting the Inclusive Education Framework (Pajaro-Marin, 2017; Dacalos, 2021).

Statement	Mean	SD	QD
I take part in school programs like celebrations, assemblies, and awareness campaigns.	3.26	0.79	Always
I volunteer in school activities whenever possible.	3.11	0.80	Most of the time
Overall Mean	3.19	0.61	Most of the time

Table 5 Level of Participation of Minority Group Learners in terms of School Events and Programs

Engagement in structured school events was moderate to high (Mean = 3.19, SD = 0.61), with learners favoring organized programs such as assemblies and awareness campaigns. Voluntary activities had slightly lower participation, suggesting that structured settings better facilitate inclusion and engagement (Cornell & Kalt, 1998; Lopez & Escueta, 2020).

Statement	Mean	SD	QD
I hold a position in class or school organizations.	3.04	0.88	Most of the time
I participate in decision-making or planning activities in school.	3.23	0.80	Most of the time
Overall Mean	3.14	0.67	Most of the time

Table 6 Level of Participation of Minority Group Learners in terms of Leadership or Representation Roles

Learners reported moderate engagement in leadership roles (Mean = 3.14, SD = 0.67). Participation was higher in decision-making activities (Mean = 3.23, SD = 0.80) than holding formal positions (Mean = 3.04, SD = 0.88), reflecting partial empowerment consistent with Arnstein's Ladder of Citizen Participation (1969). Structured leadership opportunities can enhance minority learners' self-efficacy and inclusion (Pajaro-Marin, 2017).

Statement	Mean	SD	QD
My teachers support me in learning activities.	3.64	0.63	Strongly Agree
I am given equal opportunities to participate in class activities.	3.57	0.51	Strongly Agree
I am encouraged to ask questions and share my ideas.	3.36	0.66	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.52	0.39	Strongly Agree

Table 7. Experiences of Minority Group Learners Regarding Inclusion in terms of Academic Inclusion

Learners expressed strong agreement regarding academic inclusion (Mean = 3.52, SD = 0.39). Teacher support was rated highest (Mean = 3.64, SD = 0.63), while encouragement to ask questions scored slightly lower (Mean = 3.36, SD = 0.66). Culturally responsive pedagogy supports academic engagement and empowerment (Battiste & Youngblood Henderson, 2000; Brayboy, 2005).

Statement	Mean	SD	QD
I have friends from different backgrounds in my class.	3.42	0.65	Strongly Agree
I feel accepted by my classmates.	3.52	0.63	Strongly Agree
I can freely express myself in school without fear of discrimination.	3.44	0.58	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.46	0.41	Strongly Agree

Table 8. Experiences of Minority Group Learners Regarding Inclusion in terms of Social Inclusion.

Overall, learners reported strong social inclusion (Mean = 3.46, SD = 0.41). Acceptance by peers scored highest (Mean = 3.52, SD = 0.63), and friendships across backgrounds were slightly lower (Mean = 3.42, SD = 0.65). These results underscore the importance of inclusive peer networks and collaborative learning for minority learners (Silver, 1994; Garcia & Nguyen, 2025).

Statement	Mean	SD	QD
1. My cultural practices or traditions are respected in school.	3.39	0.60	Strongly Agree
2. I have opportunities to share my culture with others.	3.27	0.65	Strongly Agree
3. I feel that my identity is recognized and valued in school.	3.41	0.57	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.36	0.36	

Table 9 Experiences of Minority Group Learners Regarding Inclusion in terms of Cultural Inclusion

Learners strongly agreed that their cultural identity was respected (Mean = 3.36, SD = 0.36). Recognition of personal identity scored highest (Mean = 3.41, SD = 0.57), while opportunities to share culture were lowest (Mean = 3.27, SD = 0.65). Findings highlight the need for structured programs to actively promote cultural expression, in line with Banks' Multicultural Education Framework (Banks, 2015; Gay, 2010).

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Remarks
Classroom participation	Between Groups	.211	2	.106	.504	.605	Not Significant
	Within Groups	31.023	148	.210			
	Total	31.234	150				
Co-curricular activities	Between Groups	.738	2	.369	.755	.472	Not Significant
	Within Groups	72.371	148	.489			
	Total	73.109	150				
School events and programs	Between Groups	1.987	2	.994	2.758	.067	Not Significant
	Within Groups	53.321	148	.360			
	Total	55.308	150				
Leadership or representation roles	Between Groups	.168	2	.084	.183	.833	Not Significant
	Within Groups	67.799	148	.458			
	Total	67.967	150				

Table 10 Difference in the Level of Participation when Respondents are Grouped According to their Profile in terms of Grade Level (n=151)

ANOVA results showed no significant differences in participation (classroom, co-curricular, school events, leadership) or experiences of inclusion (academic, social, cultural) across Grades 4–6 ($p > 0.05$), suggesting equal access and consistent inclusive practices at all grade levels.

t-test for Equality of Means							Remarks	
		T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Means Male	Means Female	Mean Difference	
Classroom participation		-.036	149	.972	3.3167	3.3195	-.00274	Not Significant
Co-curricular activities		-.910	149	.364	3.0603	3.1667	-.10632	
School events and programs		.342	149	.733	3.2069	3.1720	.03485	
Leadership or representation roles		.155	149	.877	3.1466	3.1290	.01752	

Table 11. Difference in the Level of Participation when Respondents are Grouped According to their Profile in terms of Gender (n=151)

Independent t-tests revealed no significant differences in participation or inclusion between male and female learners ($p > 0.05$), indicating equitable gender inclusion consistent with UNESCO (2017) and inclusive education frameworks (Avramidis & Norwich, 2002).

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Remarks
Classroom participation	Between Groups	.106	2	.053	.252	.778	Not Significant
	Within Groups	31.128	148	.210			
	Total	31.234	150				
Co-curricular activities	Between Groups	1.325	2	.663	1.366	.258	Not Significant

School events and programs	and	Within Groups	71.784	148	.485	.915	.403	Not Significant
		Total	73.109	150				
		Between Groups	.676	2	.338			
		Within Groups	54.632	148	.369			
Leadership representation roles	or	Total	55.308	150		4.902	.009	Significant
		Between Groups	4.223	2	2.111			
		Within Groups	63.744	148	.431			
		Total	67.967	150				

Table 12. Difference in the Level of Participation when Respondents are Grouped According to their Profile in terms of Minority Status (n=151)

ANOVA indicated no significant differences in classroom participation, co-curricular activities, or school events ($p > 0.05$). However, leadership roles showed a significant difference ($F = 4.902, p = 0.009$), suggesting disparities in access to formal representation. Institutional and socio-cultural barriers may limit leadership opportunities for some minority groups (Molintas, 2019; Alcantara & Nelles, 2014). Inclusion must extend beyond participation to representation to ensure equity.

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Remarks
Academic inclusion	Between Groups	.116	2	.058	.369	.692	Not Significant
	Within Groups	23.197	148	.157			
	Total	23.313	150				
Social inclusion	Between Groups	.178	2	.089	.537	.585	Not Significant
	Within Groups	24.555	148	.166			
	Total	24.733	150				
Cultural inclusion	Between Groups	.029	2	.014	.109	.896	Not Significant
	Within Groups	19.409	148	.131			
	Total	19.437	150				

Table 13 Difference in the Experiences of Inclusion when Respondents are Grouped According to their Profile in terms of Grade Level (n=151)

Table 13 demonstrates that grade level does not significantly influence learners' experiences of academic, social, or cultural inclusion. F-values for academic, social, and cultural inclusion are 0.369, 0.537, and 0.109, respectively, with all p-values exceeding 0.05. This suggests that learners in Grades 4, 5, and 6 experience inclusion similarly, likely due to consistent school policies and inclusive teaching practices across grades. The descriptive statistics further support the uniformity of experiences. Loreman, Deppeler, and Harvey (2010) note that inclusive programs, such as differentiated instruction and culturally responsive pedagogy, ensure equitable experiences across grade levels.

The findings underscore the importance of implementing inclusive practices that transcend grade distinctions. Schools and educators should continue fostering academic, social, and cultural inclusion as part of holistic learner development, consistent with the Social Inclusion Theory (Silver, 1994) and Inclusive Education principles.

	t-test for Equality of Means						Remarks
	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Means		Mean Difference	
				Male	Female		
Academic inclusion	-5.18	149	.605	3.5003	3.5346	-.03428	Not Significant
Social inclusion	-1.005	149	.317	3.4195	3.4877	-.06826	Not Significant
Cultural inclusion	1.371	149	.172	3.4083	3.3259	.08236	Not Significant

Table 14 Difference in the Experiences of Inclusion when Respondents are Grouped According to their Profile in terms of Sex (n=151)

No significant differences were observed in inclusion experiences between male and female learners. Both genders reported comparable levels of academic, social, and cultural inclusion, indicating effective gender-neutral practices in teaching, co-curricular activities, and school policy. This aligns with research by Avramidis and Norwich (2002), who argued that inclusive educational environments that implement culturally responsive and non-discriminatory practices mitigate differences in students' experiences based on demographic characteristics such as gender. In addition, the result suggests that male and female students are equally likely to engage in classroom discussions, participate in school events, and feel accepted by peers and teachers, reflecting equitable learning conditions. Schools should sustain gender-inclusive

strategies, ensuring all learners, regardless of sex, can access learning opportunities, participate socially, and engage culturally. Gender-sensitive teacher training and inclusive curriculum design are recommended to maintain and strengthen equitable experiences.

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Remarks
Academic inclusion	Between Groups	.107	2	.053	.340	.712	Not Significant
	Within Groups	23.206	148	.157			
	Total	23.313	150				
Social inclusion	Between Groups	.076	2	.038	.228	.796	Not Significant
	Within Groups	24.657	148	.167			
	Total	24.733	150				
Cultural inclusion	Between Groups	.470	2	.235	1.835	.163	Not Significant
	Within Groups	18.967	148	.128			
	Total	19.437	150				

Table 15. Difference in the Experiences of Inclusion when Respondents are Grouped According to their Profile in terms of Minority Status (n=151)

Minority status did not significantly affect learners' experiences of inclusion across academic, social, or cultural dimensions. Indigenous Peoples (IP) and other marginalized groups reported similar levels of inclusion, demonstrating that the school's policies, teaching strategies, and cultural programs foster an environment of equity. These findings are consistent with the framework of Inclusive Education (Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011), which emphasizes universal design and culturally responsive practices to support diverse learners. The results suggest that when minority students are provided with equal access to academic resources, social interactions, and culturally relevant activities, disparities based on minority status are minimized.

Schools should maintain and strengthen inclusive policies and programs that promote participation and equity for minority learners. Programs emphasizing intercultural understanding, social collaboration, and academic support should be prioritized to ensure all students, regardless of minority status, can thrive in the school environment.

	r-value	p	Remarks
Academic inclusion	.186*	.022	Significant
Social inclusion	.388**	.000	Significant
Cultural inclusion	.232**	.004	Significant
Overall Experience in inclusion	.400**	.000	Significant

Table 16. Relationship Between the Learners' Level of Participation in terms of Classroom Participation and their Experiences on Inclusion (n=151)

Classroom participation was positively correlated with all dimensions of inclusion. Learners who actively engage in discussions, answer questions, and complete tasks feel more academically supported, socially connected, and culturally recognized. This supports Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory, which posits that active engagement enhances confidence and social integration, and Ainscow's (2005) argument that participatory classroom settings improve overall inclusion. The stronger correlations with social and overall inclusion suggest that active engagement not only supports academic success but also strengthens social bonds and the learner's sense of belonging. These findings highlight classroom participation as a critical avenue for fostering inclusive environments where learners are empowered to contribute meaningfully.

Teachers should employ interactive teaching methods, group-based learning, and positive feedback to promote active participation. Encouraging all students to voice opinions and collaborate can enhance inclusive experiences across academic, social, and cultural dimensions.

	r-value	p	Remarks
Academic inclusion	.051	.531	Not Significant
Social inclusion	.256**	.001	Significant
Cultural inclusion	.135	.099	Not Significant
Overall Experience in inclusion	.220**	.007	Significant

Table 17 Relationship Between the Learners' Level of Participation in terms of Co-curricular Activities and their Experiences on Inclusion (n=151)

Participation in co-curricular activities was significantly associated with social inclusion and overall inclusion, but not with academic or cultural inclusion. This indicates that while such activities promote peer interaction, social networks, and connectedness (Eccles & Barber, 1999), they may not directly influence academic engagement or cultural recognition within the classroom. The social benefits of co-curricular involvement can be substantial, as learners develop interpersonal skills, form friendships, and establish peer support systems. However, academic and cultural inclusion may require intentional classroom integration and culturally responsive teaching to ensure that co-curricular benefits extend to learning outcomes.

Schools should encourage minority learners' participation in co-curricular programs while integrating academic and cultural elements into these activities. Coordinated efforts between classroom and extracurricular initiatives can maximize inclusive experiences.

	r-value	p	Remarks
Academic inclusion	.118	.150	Not Significant
Social inclusion	.084	.307	Not Significant
Cultural inclusion	.153	.061	Not Significant
Overall Experience in inclusion	.173*	.034	Significant

Table 18 Relationship Between the Learners' Level of Participation in terms of School Events and Programs and their Experiences on Inclusion (n=151)

Involvement in school-wide events, such as assemblies, celebrations, and awareness campaigns, was only significantly correlated with overall inclusion. While these activities help learners feel generally recognized and included in the school community (Lynch & Lodge, 2002), they may not directly impact academic, social, or cultural inclusion, which often require sustained interaction and engagement within classrooms and peer groups.

School-wide events should be promoted to enhance a general sense of belonging, but targeted strategies—such as classroom collaboration, culturally responsive projects, and social integration programs—should complement these events to foster comprehensive inclusion.

	r-value	p	Remarks
Academic inclusion	-.114	.165	Not Significant
Social inclusion	.225**	.005	Significant
Cultural inclusion	.190*	.019	Significant
Overall Experience in inclusion	.145	.075	Not Significant

Table 19 Relationship Between the Learners' Level of Participation in terms of Leadership or Representation Roles and Programs and their Experiences on Inclusion (n=151)

Participation in leadership or representation roles was positively correlated with social and cultural inclusion but not academic inclusion. Engaging in decision-making and leadership activities strengthens learners' social identity and cultural recognition, providing opportunities to develop confidence, collaboration skills, and cultural expression (Kearney, 2010). The absence of a significant correlation with academic inclusion suggests that leadership experience alone does not guarantee classroom engagement or academic achievement, highlighting the need for integrated academic support alongside leadership development.

Schools should provide meaningful leadership opportunities for minority learners to enhance social and cultural inclusion while pairing these programs with classroom-based interventions to support academic inclusion. Leadership, empowerment, and recognition of cultural identity are essential pillars of a holistic Inclusive Education framework.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings of this study indicate that minority students in the selected public elementary schools of San Fernando, Bukidnon, generally experience equitable inclusion across academic, social, and cultural dimensions. Interactive and supportive classroom environments emerged as the strongest predictors of positive inclusion experiences, highlighting classroom participation as the most influential factor. While participation did not significantly differ across grade levels or gender, disparities in leadership roles suggest that certain minority groups may face structural barriers in formal representation. Overall, the study underscores that active participation is a critical component of inclusion, and inclusive educational practices facilitate equitable engagement among minority learners.

Students should be encouraged to actively engage in classroom discussions, co-curricular activities, and leadership roles to strengthen their academic, social, and cultural integration within the school community.

Teachers are advised to consistently implement interactive, collaborative, and culturally responsive teaching practices that foster meaningful classroom engagement, given its strong correlation with positive experiences of inclusion.

Schools should develop structured programs and activities that allow minority learners to express, celebrate, and incorporate their cultural identities into both the curriculum and school-wide initiatives.

School administrators need to review and strengthen leadership selection processes to ensure fair representation of all minority groups in formal roles and decision-making committees. Establishing mentorship and empowerment programs can enhance confidence, leadership skills, and self-efficacy, particularly for underrepresented groups.

The findings can guide Valencia Colleges (Bukidnon) Incorporated, especially the School of Graduate Studies, in designing research-based extension programs and professional development initiatives that promote inclusive educational practices in partner public schools.

Subsequent studies may replicate or extend this research to other districts or provinces to validate the findings, compare contexts, and further explore structural factors that influence minority participation and inclusion.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.